

Efforts of Laid-off Women In Optimizing Online Learning During Quarantine

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Abstract: When online learning is carried out, teachers and parents try their best to develop various methods to attract and motivate students to be active, online learning or e-learning develops from the tradition of distance education which then maximizes its application during quarantine due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This research was conducted with the aim of looking at the magnitude of the efforts of women who have experienced layoffs and their role in optimizing online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic quarantine. This study uses a qualitative research method with a case study approach by using purposive in withdrawing subjects, researchers make clear and in-depth observations by collecting data through documentation, interviews and observations. The research was conducted in a garment factory in the Pulogadung industrial area, East Jakarta. This research found that online learning, which requires good technology and infrastructure, will be made the maximum effort for laid-off women to meet their children's learning needs if they have resilience.

Keywords: Laid off women, Learning, Online

I. Introduction

In essence, distance learning has long been implemented in several developed countries in the world, this learning is considered very effective for reaching students who are far from the study location. However, in general, distance learning is mostly implemented by senior and higher secondary education. In his research (Kerr, Rynearson & Kerr, 2006) he found that higher education had been significantly influenced by the proliferation of online forms, even though at that time online learning was still experiencing obstacles. In its application, of course online learning is not only very helpful for classroom learning activities, in his view (Kauffman, 2015) reveals that the online learning environment presents unique challenges about how to involve students in developing discipline-specific conceptual procedural knowledge. When online learning is carried out, the teacher makes every effort to develop various methods to attract and motivate students to be active, online learning or e-learning develops from the tradition of distance education. Distance education involves various forms of learning at all levels that are not under the continuous and direct supervision of tutors who are present with their students in the lecture hall or in the same place (Holmberg, 1986). Even though the application of online learning is still being

debated, many teachers often question how to authenticate online classroom learning activities with classical learning in class (Kruger-Ross & Waters, 2013). Based on data obtained through <http://indonesia.ureport.in/opinion>, it was found that 72% of children aged 15-19 years experienced boredom while participating in home learning which was marked in red.

Figure 1. Online Learning Survey

Source: <http://indonesia.ureport.in/opinion/4283/>

During the COVID-19 pandemic, all sectors were paralyzed, including the education sector and industry, so policies for conducting study activities, worship, and various other activities had to be carried out at home to break the chain of the Corona Virus. The increasing proportion of women in the world of work and the global economic crisis due to the current pandemic have made women the target population for job loss. The condition was also exacerbated by the number of mothers who had experienced layoffs as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, based on www.cnnindonesia.com the Indonesian Minister of Manpower revealed that as of January 2021 there were 623,407 female workers affected by the layoffs of the COVID-19 pandemic, this figure is substantially lower than the total men who have been laid off. However, the burden experienced by women who experience layoffs is greater than that of men.

Figure 2. 2021 Unemployment Graph

Source: <https://www.bps.go.id/website/images/Tenaga-Kerja-Agustus-2021-1-ind.jpg>

The figure above explains the percentage of the open unemployment rate for men and women until August 2021 which continues to increase by 0.7 percent compared to February 2021. This condition is certainly not easy for

women who have experienced layoffs and still have to provide learning support to their children during online learning activities, the full presence of parents is very necessary so that students understand the subject matter presented by the teacher. Through data obtained through <https://repositori.kemdikbud.go.id> related to the study from home survey, it turns out that the presence of parents does not always provide learning support for students.

Figure 3. Study From Home Survey

Source: <https://repositori.kemdikbud.go.id>

The data above on the indicator of the role of parents in providing assistance, there are 14.1% who strongly agree that their parents support online learning, while there are 13.8% of parents who accompany children during online learning. The data is obtained randomly and is not limited to students whose parents have been laid off. Psychologically, of course, women who experience layoffs are very hard hit, especially if it turns out that these women are the backbone of the family so that they have multiple roles at home, then facing layoffs is not an easy thing for them. In his view (Dew, Bromet, & Penkower, 1992) revealed that the occurrence of layoffs and the duration of time received during layoffs were significantly associated with an increase in depressive symptoms, but not anxiety-related symptoms, even after the effect of pre-discharge psychological symptoms, social support. and work stress are considered. This view certainly applies to both female and male workers, despite the fact that when receiving layoffs, married women show a greater tendency to become accustomed to stress after being laid off than unmarried women (Nuttman-Shwartz & Gadot, 2012) . This research was conducted with the aim of looking at the magnitude of the efforts of women who have experienced layoffs and their role in optimizing online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic quarantine.

II. Theoretical review

Working Woman

In everyday life in the world of work, women are often seen as lacking the ability to lead because they are seen as creatures that use their feelings too much and find it difficult to make decisions wisely, this view is very attached to women until now (Tuwu, 2018). Even though in reality women's economic welfare can generally increase if women have an independent source of income, their income certainly has an impact on increasing self-esteem, improving family economic conditions and building a community of fellow women to support each other (Ahmad & Khan, 2018). The entry of women into the wider community in the world of work is due to various factors, including: higher education so that they are ready to compete with men, the desire to develop and self-actualize or even to earn income to meet household needs (Hidayati, 2015). A very sharp view of working women is expressed

(Tindangen, Engka & Wauran, 2020) the life changes that occur along with women's efforts to achieve a prosperous life, despite the limitations of time, dimensions, and effort.

Impact of layoffs

Layoffs in the world of work not only have an impact on workers but also for companies, company reputation may be one of the strategic resources. & O'Shaughnessy, 2005). Layoffs have a big impact both for the company and for employees. One of the impacts that will be experienced by the company is to set a strategy to maintain the stability of the company together with the surviving workforce, while employees who experience layoffs can experience psychological disorders and can have an impact on criminal acts (Achiel, Soffy , Eka & Kumaya, 2020).

Online Learning

Online learning is a part of distance learning which involves technology with internet networks (Asmuni, 2020). In its application, online learning can be carried out between teachers and students simultaneously with the help of various applications such as whatsapp, telegram, zoom meeting, google class room, quipper school, teacher's room, youtube, tiktok, and various other applications in order to support online learning (Dewi & Sadjarto, 2021). In its application, online learning does not always help distance learning activities, the obstacles found in online learning include limited online learning facilities and infrastructure such as internet networks, laptop or PC learning devices that do not meet or do not exist (Haryadi & Selviani, 2021).

Benefits of Online Learning

Online learning in its application really helps students with the flexibility of time, online learning can be done anytime and anywhere so that the interaction of educators with students can take place both synchronously and asynchronously (Isman, 2016). During the COVID-19 pandemic spreading throughout the world, learning is very useful and helps the world of education including Indonesia, distance or online learning is one of the innovations in the world of education so that teaching and learning activities can continue in a virtual form (Halimatusadiya, Dewi, & Khoimatun, 2022) . In its implementation, online learning in junior high school education units has its own challenges for educators in constructing interesting learning, so that the tasks and responsibilities are felt to be very heavy (Buton, Soumokil & Tuharea, 2022).

Research Methodology

The method in this study uses a qualitative research method with a case study approach with purposive sampling. Case studies are descriptive analysis research, researchers make clear and in-depth observations by collecting data through documentation, interviews and observations. The research was conducted in a garment factory in the Pulogadung industrial area, East Jakarta. The subjects of this study were students and mothers who were victims of layoffs. The research subjects were very important in helping to collect data about student learning outcomes

during school from home.

III. Results and Discussion

This research was conducted in Pulo Gadung, East Jakarta. Respondents in this study were mothers of layoff victims who mostly worked in the Cakung industrial area, Jakarta. The respondent sampling technique was carried out purposively, which became the informant criteria in this study were women who worked in industrial area factories starting from textile, food, medicine, household appliances and chemical factories who had children studying junior high school (SMP) in Pulogadung, East Jakarta. Based on the results of interviews conducted with 25 female victims of layoffs, it was very difficult for them to be able to meet their online learning needs during the pandemic. The need for learning devices includes computers, android, internet and wifi networks, in the web-based learning era at least students need internet and wifi networks to be able to meet their learning needs. In the even semester of the 2020/2021 academic year, in an interview conducted on December 25, 2021, KM students had great difficulty sharing cellphones and laptops to study with their younger siblings at home, even though the school currently provided them with Chromebook loans, it was still difficult for them to coordinate because they did not have wifi or a network. maximum internet for learning. KM also explained that what students often do to maximize the collection of assignments, especially project-based assignments, is to get a free quota from the government, buy a weekly quota, go to a friend's or neighbor's house that has wifi and occasionally they go to a fast food restaurant. to get wifi network for free. Based on the results of interviews and filling in google foam, 44% of women who were laid off agreed that they had difficulty fulfilling online learning media, both wifi, quota, PCs, laptops and mobile phones.

Figure 1. Diagram of Parental Difficulties in Providing Online Learning Media

By learning fast food restaurants that have wifi, it is felt that it is very helpful for students to meet the needs of web-based online learning. Other needs such as laptops, cellphones or Android students try to take turns with younger siblings and parents to be able to carry out online learning activities, at the first start of online activities students are very stressed and bored because they have to study at home for months since. JN in an interview conducted on December 19 2021 revealed that the respondent was very bored, stressed, and forced several times to go to a friend's house so they could study together or just meet to laugh, although of course not all friends could be visited because many complexes were closed at that time .

The results of this study show that healthy and happy children are the main reason they survive and stay strong. This can be seen from the questionnaire which answered 72% strongly agreed and 28% agreed that children should continue to study online and carry out education properly with makeshift devices.

Figure 2. Diagram Parents continue to provide education

Various efforts made by mothers in very difficult conditions after being laid off to meet the needs of online learning, it is not easy for parents, especially mothers, to face layoffs amid the conditions of the COVID-19 Pandemic. There is no money coming in but needs must continue, children must continue to go to school, school needs must still be met, and their nutrition must still be considered. Even though their mental condition is very unstable, mothers always try to build self-motivation and resilience in various ways. One of them is by telling each other through the WAG (whatsapp group), through the WAG the mothers tell each other their problems. In addition, through this community mothers can support, strengthen and comfort one another. Through this community, mothers are helped to re-focus on the conditions they are running. Parents also play an active role in accompanying children during online learning activities, mothers are expected to play an active role in student learning activities. In an interview conducted on November 29 2021, they revealed that the respondent actually did not understand the learning material in the junior high school education unit. However, because the child is with him every day, the respondent must deliberately give his time and attention to the student.

Figure 3. Diagram of Assistance for Children Studying at Home

Based on the questionnaire data, it was found that 48% of respondents strongly agreed and 52% agreed out of a total of 25 respondents providing assistance to students while implementing online learning due to the COVID-19 pandemic was important during layoffs. Maximum assistance will certainly have an impact on student learning outcomes and the emotional closeness of children and mothers.

IV. Conclusion

Online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic dealt a hard blow to women who had experienced layoffs. In the midst of limited funds and cessation of income but having to be able to meet students' learning needs is certainly not easy, but the resilience of women who have experienced layoffs is the most important thing to be able to deal with these difficult conditions. Online learning that requires good technology and infrastructure will be made as much effort as possible for women who have resilience.

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